

A Study on Job Satisfaction of Employees In a.J. Hospital & Research Center, Mangalore

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ABSTRACT

A healthy productive organization is one in which constructive and share positive attitude towards the purpose of their job and the identification of their job with role or objective of their organization. If the people employed in an organization are well looked after and understood, if their needs are studied and met then they are the people who are such a source of strength that can take the organization to magnanimous heights of glory and achievements to instill healthy atmosphere in their organization.

Job satisfaction refers to one's feeling or state of mind regarding nature of their work. Job can be influenced by the variety of factors like quality of one's relationship with their supervisor, quality of physical environment in which they work, degree of fulfillment in their work, etc. The purpose of this study was to investigate predictors of Job Satisfaction in an Organization. For decades, job satisfaction has been one of the most extensively researched concepts in work and organizational psychology. In 1984, Young defined job satisfaction as "the affective reaction that

employees have about their jobs”. According to Young, job satisfaction has implications for the individual related to physical and mental health, for the organization related to the acceptance of and good performance of the job, and for society related to quality and quantity of life.

Key words: Satisfaction, positive attitude, employees, work and organizational psychology.

Introduction

A primary aim of any organization is to achieve the most effective utilization of resources that has as its disposal. The principal resources have been defined as money, man, material amongst the most important resource which needs to be properly, managed and handled by man. Job satisfaction is the fulfillment, gratification, and enjoyment that comes from work. It's not just the money or the fringe benefits, but the feelings employees receive from the work itself.

Job Satisfaction is the favorableness or un-favorableness with which the employee views his work. It expresses the amount of agreement between one's expectation of the job and the rewards that the job provides. Job Satisfaction is a part of life satisfaction. The nature of one's environment of job is an important part of life as Job Satisfaction influences one's general life satisfaction. Job Satisfaction, thus, is the result of various attitudes possessed by an employee. In a narrow sense, these attitudes are related to the job under condition with such specific factors such as wages. Supervisors of employment, conditions of work, social relation on the job, prompt settlement of grievances and fair treatment by employer. However, more comprehensive approach requires that many factors are to be included before a complete understanding of job satisfaction can be obtained. Such factors as employee's age, health temperature, desire and level of aspiration should be considered. Further his family relationship, Social status, recreational outlets, activity in the organizations etc. Contribute ultimately to job satisfaction.

Human factors psychology, or ergonomics, studies the interface between workers and their machines and physical environments. Human factors psychologists specifically seek to design machines to better support the workers using them. Psychologists may be involved in design of work tools such as software, displays, or machines from the beginning of the design process or during the testing an already developed product. Human factor psychologists are also involved in the development of best design recommendations and regulations. One important aspect of

human factors psychology is enhancing worker safety. Human factors research involves efforts to understand and improve interactions between technology systems and their human operators. Human–software interactions are a large sector of this research.

Organizational psychology is the second major branch of study and practice within the discipline of industrial and organizational psychology. In organizational psychology, the focus is on social interactions and their effect on the individual and on the functioning of the organization. In this section, you will learn about the work organizational psychologists have done to understand job satisfaction, different styles of management, different styles of leadership, organizational culture, and teamwork.

Employment should be mutually rewarding experience, especially in case of service oriented organization such as hospitals. The hospital has certain expectations for productivity, dependability and cooperation, and the employees have certain expectations for good pay, benefits, quality supervision, and good working environments.

There are two basic source of job satisfaction:

1. The employees pride in their craft
2. The physical environment both physical and interpersonal.

The ability to produce the quality of the work, the opportunity to learn and express creativity, the sense of pride in their profession, the recognition for a job well done, the ability to work well in a team, the satisfaction derived from relationship at work, the opportunity to experience personal growth and the rewards from a physically supportive work environment are all factors that impact on job satisfaction.

Review of literature

Origo and Pagani1 (2008) investigated the relationship between flexibility and Job Satisfaction. In their analysis they verified whether various aspects of flexibility namely functional and quantitative flexibility, produce different impact on overall extrinsic and intrinsic Job Satisfaction. They also tested whether the impact of flexibility on Job Satisfaction varied with workers characteristics. Empirical evidence was based on a representative sample of European employees taken from a specific wave of the Euro barometer Survey. The study found that there was a positive link between functional flexibility and Job Satisfaction and there was either no

effect or a negative impact of quantitative flexibility. The positive impact of functional flexibility was greater when compared to the satisfaction for intrinsic aspects of the job. Estimate by workers characteristics highlighted interesting differences by age, skill and country of residence.

NilufarAhsan (2009) investigated the relationship between Job stress and Job Satisfaction. The study conducted in a Public University in Klang Valley area in Malaysia and 300 respondents were selected as a sample of the study. The determinants of job stress that have been examined under this study include management role, relationship with others, work load pressure, homework interface, role ambiguity and performance pressure. The results of the study revealed that the association between relationship with others and job stress is not significant. The relationship between workload pressure and job stress, role ambiguity and job stress is significant. The study concluded that the motivation is a key factor as well in affecting job stress among employees. Employees who were highly motivated will feel happier and were more willing to work for the organization.

Salman Khalid(2010) examined Job Satisfaction level of Bank Employees in Punjab Province. The information collected from 144 respondents from four Banks employees who were randomly selected from both public and private sector banks. Five components of Job Satisfaction such as work, pay, promotion, salary and recognition were examined besides overall Job Satisfaction. The findings of the study indicated that the sectoral differences in terms of salary, promotions, job security, recognition and benefits play a significant role in influencing one's perception of job satisfaction. Private sector bank employees reported dissatisfaction in terms of Job Security.

Javed and Premarajan26 (2011) examined the influence of distributive and procedural justice on pay and Job Satisfaction. They provided that distributive justice and procedural justice had differentiating impact on Job Satisfaction and four facets of pay satisfaction i.e. level, raise, benefits and administration. The survey carried out among 122 Indian managers. It was found that the distributive justice as a more important predictor of all four dimensions of pay satisfaction and Job Satisfaction. Procedural justice was also found to be a statistically significant predictor of pay structure and Job Satisfaction.

Biswas27 (2011) studied the impact of Human Resource Management policies and practices in a globalized Indian economy and subsequently their outcome with respect to individual behavior

and performances. The data were collected from 357 managerial level employees of Indian Organizations. The result of the study found that the Job Satisfaction significantly correlated with employee performance and also showed that although discrepancies were abounding regarding individual reactions to a hitherto closed and controlled economy. The findings indicated that human resource practices in India need to adapt to contemporary practices and procedures worldwide, while at the same time maintain in its unique cultural ethos.

Industry profile

The word “Hospital” originates from the Latin ‘HOSPICE’. The word hospital, hostel and hotel all derive from the common Latin root hospice. The place or an establishment where a guest is received was called the hospitium or hospitale. The term hospital has at different times been used to refer to an institution for the aged and the infirm, a place of rest, a hostel where people lived as a small community and an institution for the care of the sick and wounded.

Hospitals in India

Early Indian rulers considered the provision of institutional care to the sick as their spiritual and temporal responsibility. The forerunners of the present hospitals can be traced to the times of Buddha, followed by Ashoka. The writings of Sushruta (6th century BC) and Charaka (200 AD) the famous surgeon and physician respectively were considered standard works for many centuries with instructions (in CharakaSamhita) for creation of hospitals, for provision of lying-in and children rooms, maintenance and sterilization of bed linen with steam and fumigation and use of syringes and other medical appliances. Medicine based on the Indian system was taught in ancient university of Taxila. CharakaSamhita, a treatise on medicine based on the teaching of Charaka was written around 600 AD and SushrutaSamhita, a treatise of surgical knowledge, was compiled during 400 AD.

The most notable of the early hospitals were those built by King Ashoka (273-232 BC). There were rituals laid down for the attendants and physicians who were enjoined to wear white clothes and promise to keep the confidence of the patients.

However, the age of Indian medicine started its decline from the Mohammedan invasions in the tenth century. The Mohammedans brought with them their Hakims who followed the Greek

system of medicine which came to be known as “Yunani”. This system and its physicians started to prosper at the expense of Ayurveda and its Vaidya’s. However, the influence of Ayurveda continued in the south.

The Modern system of medicine in India was introduced in the 17th century with the arrival of European Christian Missionaries in South India. In the 17th century, the East India Company established its first hospital in 1664 at Chennai for its soldiers and in 1668 for the civilian population. European doctors started getting popular and during the latter part of 18th and early 19th century, there was a steady growth of a modern system of medical practice and hospitals, pushing the indigenous system to the background. Organized medical training was started with the first medical college opening in Calcutta in 1835, two in Delhi in 1835 and 1836, followed by Mumbai in 1845 and Chennai in 1850.

As the British spread their political control over the country, many hospitals and dispensaries originally started to treat the army personnel was handed over to the civil administrative authorities for treating civil population. Local government and local self-government bodies (municipalities etc.) were encouraged to start dispensaries at tehsil and district level. In 1885 there were 1250 hospitals and dispensaries in British India. But the medical care scarcely reached 10 percent of the population.

World Health Organization defines Hospital as ‘an integral part of the medical and social organization which is to provide for the population complete health care, both curative and preventive; and whose out-patient services reach out into the family in its home environment. The hospital is also a Centre for the training of health workers and also for bio-social research’.

The health care services have undergone a steady metamorphosis, and the role of the hospital has changed, with the emphasis shifting from:

- Acute to chronic illness
- Curative to preventive medicine
- Restorative to comprehensive medicine
- Inpatient care to outpatient and home care
- Individual orientation to community orientation
- Isolated function to area-wise or regional function

- Tertiary and secondary to primary health care
- Episodic care to total care

Objectives: The major objectives of the study are:

- To measure the employees job satisfaction level.
- To study the employees perception towards organization.
- To study the attitude of the employees towards the work.
- To identify the factors that motivates the employees.
- To give suggestions for the growth & perspective of the company.

The objective of the study is also classified into primary and secondary objectives as they are follows: **Primary objective:** The primary objective of this study is to study the job satisfaction level of employees and to suggest measures, which might be help the organization in improving the “job satisfaction level” among the employees. **Secondary objectives:** To understand the level of employee job satisfaction and factors which make the employees desirable in the hospital policies, working conditions and other factors. To find out the satisfaction level regarding the compensation plans, transparency and leadership. To analyze employee loyalty towards company and to understand the commitment of management towards employees, in terms of trust empowerment etc. To evaluate the alternative preferences of employees. To analyze the performance of employees. To study the areas of improvement & give suggestions for future improvement of A.J. Hospital and Research Center

Secondary data

Secondary data is the data which is already been collected and assembled. This data is available with the company or firm and it can also be got from newspapers, periodicals magazines etc.

- Internet site
- Company profile
- HR articles
- Department manuals

Findings

The study as “A study to access the job satisfaction among the staffs of nursing department in A.J Hospital & Research Centre, Mangalore” is undertaken with the objective to access the level of job satisfaction and present working condition, procedure and policy of the employees.

A consistently high level of employee’s motivation and commitment are the key factors in developing a positive working environment. In this study there is most of the staffs are happy with their environment because there is a lot of challenging work and there is a good team work among the staffs it helps to motivate the employees work hard and it helps them to build confidence in their life.

- It was found that most of the nursing department work as team. Its shows a positive result in their work as well as good relationship.
- According to the study majority of the staffs stated that there is the periodical training facility is conducting which helps them to minimize their mistakes and which is helps for future career development.
- It was found that there is good working condition.
- It was found that majority of staffs happy with their extra-curricular activities. As there is a lot of challenging activities which built healthy relationship employees and management.
- It was found that some of the employees are unhappy about compensation package
- It was found that majority of staffs are agreed hospital as good place to work as it is more safety and its give lot experience and which gives lot of knowledge.

Conclusion

The study clearly shows that majority of staff agree that they are happy about the present working procedures and conditions, safety measures, hospital leadership, compensation benefits etc. Also, the staffs are proud to work for the organization and possess a strong feeling as being an integral part of the hospital as there is good team work and better co-ordination among the staff. Therefore, I can say that overall job satisfaction level of employees in the hospital is good.

However, it is also been found that there are certain crucial areas where the staff are not satisfied like grievance handling, canteen and hostel facilities, statutory and non-statutory facilities. These needs to be improved which makes the employees a better work place.

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